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FIELD TRIP

Vigo Pilot and placer deposits at Vao Beach

11 June 2025

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Funded by
the European Union

VIGO, SPAIN

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VIGO PILOT (exploration phase) Marine mineral resources in shallow water

Mineral-metallogenic map of Galicia 1:400 000 (IGME, 1982)

Previous marine mineral (regional) data

Previous marine mineral (local) data and the S34I visited areas

Shoreline tasks in five field trips

Surface placer identification

Pegmatitic veins identification

Cartography

Georadar survey

Georadar survey

Sand sampling

Cartography using PNOA and UAV surveys

Field observations and intertidal dynamics

Diferential-GPS point

Subsoil exploration

Shallow water tasks in three field trips

Shallow water activities (70-15 m)

UHI and ROV equipment

UHI and ROV recording

Safety briefing and coordination

UHI and ROV testing

Shallow water activities (<5 m)

Van Veen dredges

Navigation

Underwater drone testing and repairing

Shallow water sample

Underwater drone operating

Spectroradiometer measure

Underwater drone sampling

Underwater drone images

VIGO PILOT (exploration phase) Marine mineral resources in shallow water

Aerial activities in one field trip

UAV operating

Placer mineral at Santa Marta Beach (UAV image)

UAV operating

Placer mineral at Vao Beach (UAV image)

Placer mineral in ripples at Vao Beach (UAV image)

Laboratory activities

Heavy minerals separation and identification

Spectral measurements

Four methods using Earth Observation capabilities

① Integration of traditional geological methodologies with EO techniques for delineating CRM prospective areas for placer deposits

② Spectral unmixing algorithms for innovative UHI data processing

③ A new EO methodology for the detection and/or verification detection of heavy mineral deposits in coastal regions

④ Satellite Derived Bathymetry (SDB) for shallow waters using nested boosting techniques

Placer deposit in Vao Beach

Coarse heavy minerals (marine influence)

Fine heavy minerals (eolic influence)

UAV image and cartography (<math><0.03\text{ m/pixel}</math>)

PNOA image and cartography (0.15 m/pixel)

Placer deposit in Vao Beach

Placer mineral (surface and subsoil)

Heavy minerals in transition zone

UAV image and cartography (<0.03 m/pixel)

PNOA image and cartography (0.15 m/pixel)

Georadar survey

Article

Comparative Performance of Sentinel-2 and Landsat-9 Data for Raw Materials' Exploration Onshore and in Coastal Areas

Morgana Carvalho¹, Joana Cardoso-Fernandes¹, Francisco Javier González² and Ana Claudia Teodoro^{1,*}

Band ratios, PCA and RGB applied to Landsat 9 and Sentinel 2

Ferric iron

Iron oxides

Hydrothermal alteration

Sentinel 2

Landsat 9

Article

Spectral Angle Mapper Application Using Sentinel-2 in Coastal Placer Deposits in Vigo Estuary, Northwest Spain

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SAM application to Sentinel 2

Sentinel 2 escene

Validation using UAV flight and cartography

Result using spectra 1

Result using spectra 2

